

The Importance of Portfolio in Language Teaching and Methods of Using it

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ABSTRACT

This article describes experiences of using portfolios as an instrument for professional development during a one-year pre-service teacher education course for language graduates. The context and the geographic point of the article is to identify fairly principally working process of portfolios. Author illustrates cognitive content of portfolios such as, a) identifying a trainee's learning procedure over time, b) illustrating an individual's district, c) the entertainment complexity of pedagogue's life, d) primarily stimulate reflection. By this article reader can find answers on topic portfolios and how the brain characteristics influence trainees' reflective skills.

Key words: portfolio, portfolio contents, portfolio purposes, pre-service teacher, reflective skill, reflection, student teachers, reflective thinking, development, evidence.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the promotion of reflection is considered to be an essential goal in teacher education, because it is thought that reflection plays a major part in the teachers development (Barret,2005). In a primarily reflective way to teacher education, student teachers are needed to reflect on their rehearse set in order understanding, evaluating, and it is necessary modifying it. Many a Pre-service teacher teaching courses breakthrough this ability to critical, since it enables student teachers to lead their personal development. Further information that

portfolios can assist to this indispensable acquirement of reflective thinking is provided by Barto and Collins (1993) and Wade (1991), while Sherman (2007) writes about worth of portfolios: ‘In ways no other assessment method can, portfolios provide a connection to the context and personal histories of real teaching and make it possible to document the unfolding of both teaching and learning over time.

Portfolio teaching can attend to according to three purpose: Engaging of *evaluation portfolios* is valuating knowledge and/or skill (Shackelford, 2004) which can control a number of products to be assessed. *Employability portfolios* establish the evidence of learning of required skills; (Johnson and Rose,1997); an instance would be an accumulation of teacher which unutilized for classification or promotional material purposes. The aim of *professional growth portfolios* is evaluating the learning procedure, reflection, and utilizing to amuse development and growth (Donato 1997). The portfolio should illustrate that the trainees areas unit cognizant of their personal basic cognitive, process activity, and development as teachers, and that they are able to reflect on, demonstrate that process.

Introducing portfolios. Since the construct of a portfolio is bran-new to trainees, we first them to the content by providing a written handbook which includes among another belongings, a portfolio account, a explanation for utilizing: Attendant every portfolio themes, trainees compose a reflexive remark about what is their selected subject, why they have contained it, which view(s) of their development it delineate, how they have acquired, how their selected evidence symbolizes that development. The selection of subjects themes is left up to the trainees, even supposing they are required to represent a spacious scene of their development within the under mentioned four categories: teaching, supervising learners, organization and professionalization (Barton and Collins, 1993)

The subject matters of portfolio

- Page of cognitive content
- Teaching and learning hypothesis
- Between five and ten themes which development is illustrated. Each subject is consorted by various pieces of evidence, in addition reflective comment
- Conclusions which open trainee's learning (take in action design for the succeeding
- Evaluation about producing portfolio

The learning process. One of our primary causes for establishing portfolios is that they reveal the learning procedure. A trainee is able to explain a learning spiral in a portfolio. A well-constructed portfolio theme typically demonstrates the following learning procedure: firstly, the trainee looks back at a classroom, and considers on that experience, counterbalance alternative directions of action; next, she resolves on a course activeness, tries something own in lessons, cogitates addition on that activeness, and closes with what she learnt, and a new action level for the future. For example, teacher's portfolio works on two projects-one on the novel, and one which learners of that teacher made brochure-exemplifies this learning spiral, as can be seen below:

Trying something out in lessons

Reflection further on those actions

Concluding with what has been learnt; making a new action point for the future.

Complex reality. A portfolio permits a trainee to represent a complicated and veritable scene of teacher's life and revealing how various views of teacher's life and interwoven. By 'a complicated and veritable', it can be meant many various views of a trainee's professional development are interleaved, and that portfolio is able to a certain extent, reflect the veritable contexts in which trainees work.

Reflection. We agree that portfolios encourage the reflection in distinctive ways. Generally, trainee's first step in reflection is awareness of teaching aspects which trainee wants to work on selected as a portfolio theme, she gives entrance to project work. Next, new directions of working are examined. Finally, the experiments are accomplished, evaluated, and examined, questions are put, and conclusions are depicted for the future. The chance to reflect upon learning that was constructed under the program and come back to visit the web and deeper revisiting and reflecting... in the portfolio teachers can sometimes go back to something they have constructed early in the fall and then ideally they are able to say, all of experience past they had and link them to now.

Recommendations for improving reflective skills. Critically, one matter to trainees' reflective comments, or rather in need of comprehensiveness and specificity, besides their disability to see or make connection between hypotheses (theory) is engaged in university classes, and what happens in their classrooms. For example, actualization that being issue is observed commonly by prompt step or

plan to settle it without any real analysis of the issue, reading around the subject, debate with other people or reflection about potential option.

CONCLUSION

Finally, portfolios are exceedingly useful course of stimulating student teachers for working on their own individual, professional development. Portfolios have supported student teachers, trainees, and school supervisors with more insight into practical; knowledge-development, teaching behavior, and thought procedures. The student teachers have awareness of how they work as teachers, and reflecting developed skills to their practice, developing those reflective skills by creating their portfolios independently selecting of their own themes and evidence.

References:

1. Barret, C. (2005) the REFLECT Initiative: White Paper. Researching electronic portfolios and learner engagement. <http://electronicportfolios.com/portfolios.html> accessed 20.12.2008
2. Barto, J.,& Collins, A (1993). Portfolios in teacher education. *Journal of Teacher Education* 44(3),200
3. Black J.B., Turner N.J., Bower J.H. Point of view in negative comprehension, memory and production-journal of verbal learning and verbal "behavior". 1879, p. 187 to 198.
4. Donato, J.(1997): The portfolio question: A powerful synthesis of the personal and professional. *Teacher Education*, 25(1),33-43
5. Johnson, R and Rose, S (1997). Guidelines for quality in autobiographical forms of self-study research. *Educational researcher*,30(1), 13
6. Shackelford,G (2004). *The educational potential of portfolios*. Routledge: London.

7. Sherman, A. (2007). Pre-service teachers' experiences with a science education module. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 18, 525-541